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For enquiries and feedback please email: aulr@africau.edu

Graphic Design and Production: Hans**Mak** DesignsP/L
Tel: 0772 319 781/Email: hansmakdesigns@gmail.com

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The Distinction between Combatants and Civilians in International Humanitarian Law

*Amade Roberts Amana, PhD, BL. Associate Professor of Law
Faculty of Education and Legal Studies, Kampala International
University in Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania
ORCID: 0000-0003-4458-0724*

*Joshua Enemali Usman, LL.M. BL.
J. E. Usman and Associates, Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria*

Abstract

In traditional paradigms of armed conflict, combatants are clearly distinguished from civilians, and the latter is not to be deliberately attacked and is insulated from the effects of violence. While this scenario captures the aspirations of the laws of war, the reality is markedly different. Over the years, the principle of distinction has emerged as one of the cornerstones of International Humanitarian Law, upon which the orderly conduct of war and the protection of the civilian population rests. The focus of this article is to articulate the normative ways in which international humanitarian law distinguishes between combatants and civilians, and the difficulty involved in maintaining the distinction in an era of increasing intermingling of combatants and civilians in the military or war environment. The approach taken by the paper is doctrinal; therefore, an extensive analysis of the concepts of combatants and civilians is undertaken. Some of the hurdles involved in weakening the principle of distinction in modern conflicts are explored.

Keywords: Principle of Distinction, Combatants, Civilians, Attacks, Military Objectives, Armed Conflict

I. Introduction

The major casualties of war, by death, injury, forced displacement or loss of property are civilians. As the United States Army stated in its Civilian Casualty Mitigation Manual:

[i]n addition to the inherent risks from combat, a society disrupted by armed conflict will have other vulnerabilities, particularly if large numbers of civilians lack food, water, shelter, medical care, and security. Disease, starvation, dehydration, and the climate may be more threatening to civilians than casualties from Army operations.¹

Estimates of civilian deaths resulting from armed conflict vary from one source to the other, with some authorities pegging it at about ninety percent of war-related deaths.² Modern wars have become even deadlier because the theatre of confrontation has shifted from isolated, distant battle fields to the heart of densely populated cities, thereby challenging traditional norms of armed conflict, including the basic principle of distinction.

The protection of persons who are no longer participating in hostilities is a cardinal objective of International Humanitarian Law (IHL). Theoretically, persons or objects that are protected from attack are classified and separated from persons or objects that can be legitimately targeted. Participating in an attack will determine if a person has exposed himself to attack by the opposing forces or not. The judgement of the tribunal in

¹ Headquarters, United States Army Training and Doctrine Command, Civilian Casualty Mitigation, Army Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (atp) 3-37.31 (July 2012), available <https://fas.org/irp/doddir/army/atp3-37-31.pdf> accessed 30 October 2024.

² The Civilian Consequences of War, available at <https://world101.cfr.org/understanding-international-system/conflict/civilian-consequencesconflict#:~:text=However%2C%20wars%20in%20recent%20decades,four%20million%20war%2Drelated%20deaths>, accessed on 30 March 2024.

the *Prosecutor v Krnojelac*³ defined an attack as a course of conduct involving the commission of acts of violence. An attack is different from an armed conflict and even independent of it. In practice, an attack could outlast, precede, or run parallel to an armed conflict, without necessarily being a part of it.⁴

In IHL, the status of an individual is important because the rules of armed conflict determine who can legitimately take up arms. There are broadly two categories of individuals under the rules: combatants and civilians. The protection available to an individual depends upon whether he belongs to one category of individuals or the other. As much as IHL protects civilians, it also protects the military forces of the belligerents, especially under the Third Geneva Convention of 1949.⁵ Members of the armed forces are authorized to bear arms and use force. Other levels of protection are available to civilians as long as they do not directly or actively take part in hostilities.⁶ Nevertheless, due diligence must always be taken in military operations to minimize injury to civilians or damage to civilian property.

Much of the debate about the status of individuals who bear arms and take a direct part in hostilities stems from those cases where individuals who are not members of the armed forces; who do not qualify upon capture as prisoners-of-war, or who do not wear distinguishing insignia, directly engage in hostilities. At its inception, IHL was preoccupied with the protection of soldiers who were wounded in battle; *hors de combat*, or had

² *Prosecutor v Milorad Krnojelac* Case No. IT-97-25, 15 March 2002.

⁴ *Ibid* para 54.

⁵ Geneva Convention Relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War of 12 August 1949.

⁶ MN Schmitt (2009), 'Deconstructing direct participation in hostilities: the constitutive elements' 2009(42) *International Law and Politics* at 701.

fallen into the power of the adversary.⁷ Following the adoption of the Geneva Conventions of 1949, the rules of IHL were extended to provide protection to civilians. The provisions on distinction and targeting stipulate who or what may lawfully be the object of attack during armed conflicts. Acts of violence against the adversary, whether in offence or in defence, constitute attacks.⁸

There are two categories of armed conflicts: an international armed conflict (IAC) and a non-international armed conflict or internal armed conflict (NIAC).⁹ Akande has posited that the distinction between both typologies arose from historical trends in the regulation of armed conflict by international law.¹⁰ Initially, the law of war applied only to inter-state wars but after the Second World War and with the global affirmation of human rights, its application was extended to conflicts occurring within the territory of a State. The distinction is well preserved by Article 8 of the Statute of the International Criminal Court, on war crimes.

According to Article 2 common to all four Geneva Conventions of 1949, the conventions shall apply to all cases of declared war or of any other armed conflict which may arise

⁷ MS Islam, 'The Historical Evolution of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) From Earliest Societies to Modern Age' [2018] (9) (2) *Beijing Law Review*, 294-307.

⁸ Article 49 (1), Protocol Additional to The Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), of 8 June 1977.

⁹ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC). "How does Law Protect in War? - ICRC". Available at http://casebook.icrc.org/a_to_z/glossary/classification-conflict#:~:text=Therefore%2C%20the%20key%20distinction%20between,be%20classified%20as%20non%20international. Accessed on 30 October 2024.

¹⁰ Dapo Akande, 'Classification of Armed Conflicts: Relevant Legal Concepts' in Elizabeth Wilmschurst (ed), *International Law and the Classification of Conflicts* (Oxford University Press, 2012 at 1, available at <https://www.papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2132573>, accessed on 26 April 2022.

between two or more of the High Contracting Parties, even if the state of war is not recognized by one of them. Situations of partial or total occupation of the territory of a High Contracting Party by the armed forces of another State are regarded as an IAC, even if the occupation meets with no armed resistance. Civil wars are the paradigmatic example of non-international armed conflicts.¹¹ With regard to a NIAC, Article 3 common to the Geneva Conventions deals with an ‘armed conflict not of an international character occurring in the territory of one of the High Contracting Parties...’ However, the adequacy of the traditional bifurcation of armed conflicts has been questioned in recent times, especially as most contemporary conflicts do not perfectly fit into the IAC and NIAC molds.¹² For example, the Boko Haram insurgent group which originated in Nigeria has spread its operations across several African states including Cameroon, Chad, Niger and Mali. Its fighters are drawn from different nationalities fighting in, and beyond their countries of nationality. The existence of an armed conflict is crucial because it triggers the application of IHL; justifies the dichotomy between individuals as combatants and civilians, and entitles the State to use lethal force against those participating in hostilities. The distinction between the two types of conflicts has normative and practical implications on the status of individuals during the conduct of hostilities and upon their capture as well.

This article is organized into eight sections. The next section of the paper discusses the principle of distinction followed by an exploration of military objectives and civilian objects in section

¹¹ N Zamir, *Classification of Conflicts in International Humanitarian Law: The Legal Impact of Foreign Intervention in Civil Wars* (Edward Egar Publishing 2017).

¹² E Crawford, ‘Unequal Before the Law: The case for the elimination of the distinction between international and non-international armed conflict’ [2007] (20) (2) *Leiden Journal of International Law*;441–465.

3. In section 4, the article examines the concept of combatants in an international armed conflict. Section 5 addresses the status of non-state actors in a non-international armed conflict. In section 6, the paper examines the position of civilians, and what conditions predispose them to the loss of their protected status. This is followed by an examination of the notion of direct participation in hostilities in section 7. Section 8 examines the challenges to the application of the principle of distinction while concluding remarks are given in section 9.

2. The principle of distinction

Along with other legal creations, the principle of distinction is one of the cardinal parameters for measuring the legality of conduct during *jus in bello*.¹³ Distinction and protection go together, for without distinction, there can be no protection.¹⁴ For parties to the Geneva Conventions of 1949, the principle of distinction is a binding norm under the *pacta sunt servanda* doctrine, and for non-parties, a source of customary international law.¹⁵ Rudimentary forms of the principle have been found in military antiquity. Ancient warfare was conducted with a form of orderliness, no matter how minute it was. The Ramayana forbade the use of a weapon of warfare which could destroy the entire race of the enemy including those who did not bear arms.¹⁶ However, Maja Spanu has

¹³ IP Пташник, 'The challenges to the principle of distinction posed by non-international armed conflicts' *Право і суспільство* (2013) 2 at 381-383.

¹⁴ M John (2024), Analysis of the Extent of Protection Accorded to Civilians, Civilian Populations, and Civilian Objects by International Humanitarian Law in Armed Conflicts. *East African Journal of Law and Ethics*, 7(1), pp.1-14.

¹⁵ SM Bouvier, & A. A. *How Does Law Protect in War? Second, Expanded and Updated Edition. Volume II. Part III: Cases and Document*, Geneva, International Committee of the Red Cross (2006) at 734.

¹⁶ RV Radhika, 'Revisiting the Ancient Indian Laws of Warfare and Humanitarian Laws' 2017 (3)3 *IndraStra Global* at 1.

written that ‘Conventionally, the idea of protecting civilians from the effects of war, or from even being a target of the war, originated in the aftermath of World War II.’¹⁷ The rules of *jus in bello* provide directions on “how” armed conflicts should be prosecuted.¹⁸ The fulcrum upon which these principles turn is the distinction between combatants and non-combatants.¹⁹ The principle of distinction is intransgressible and foundational in IHL.²⁰ However, attacks on civilians and civilian objects are not unlawful *per se* as long as they are incidental, and not disproportionate or excessive in relation to the concrete and direct military advantage anticipated.²¹ The principle of distinction presupposes the application of precautionary measures before attacks are launched in order to avoid excessive harm to civilians, even where military advantage is anticipated.²² The implementation of the principle is of utmost importance for the protection of civilians during armed conflicts. The principle of distinction has two complimentary sides: the distinction between civilians and lawful targets on one hand, and on the other hand, the responsibility of combatants or persons who are fighting to distinguish

¹⁷ M Spanu, (2016) ‘Civilian Protection: Some Thoughts on the Historical Origins of the Norm’ (11 July 2016) available at <<https://www.iow.eui.eu/2016/07/11/civilian-protection-some-thoughts-on-the-historical-origins-of-the-norm/>>, accessed on 12 April 2022

¹⁸ R Kolb, (1997), Origin of the twin terms *jus ad bellum*/*jus in bello* *International Review of the RedCross* (1961-1997), 37(320) at 553-562.

¹⁹ Paul. H. Wise, ‘The Epidemiologic Challenge to the Conduct of War: Confronting Indirect Civilian Casualties of War’ *Dædalus*, 2017 (10)146 *The Journal of the American Academy of Arts & Sciences* at145.

²⁰ Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons, Advisory Opinion, ICJ. 8th July 1996, ¶ 79.

²¹ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), “Targeting under International Humanitarian Law,” How Does Law Protect in War?, available at <https://casebook.icrc.org/highlight/targeting-under-international-humanitarian-law#:~:text=Even%20when%20the%20target%20is,concrete%20and%20direct%20military%20advantage,> accessed on 30 October 2024.

²² A Nwotite ‘The Principle of Distinction in the Light of Civilian Protection in International Armed Conflict’ 2020 (4)2 *AJLHR* at 82.

themselves from persons who are not fighting or participating in hostilities.²³

Difficulty in observing the principle of distinction has been noted in territories where terrorism is endemic because terrorism is intended to provoke collective fear and uncertainty in the civilian population.²⁴ A second logical conclusion is that in repressive regimes, characterized by flagrant violations of human rights, there will be little or no impetus to preserve these same rights during armed conflicts. Article 52 (2) of Additional Protocol I and Article 13 (2) of Additional Protocol II prohibit acts aimed at spreading terror among the civilian population. These provisions are meant to prevent the terrorization of civilians in situations of armed conflict. Specifically, the distinction between civilians and combatants has not been implemented in the ongoing insurgency in Afghanistan. In Afghanistan, there are two major classifications of terrorist organizations: those associated with the Taliban for example, Al-Qaeda, and the Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan on one hand, and other groups which are opposed to the Taliban, for example, the Islamic State Khorasan (ISKP).²⁵ Following the withdrawal of the United States army from Afghanistan in August 2021, the country has been engulfed by insurgency. To put things in perspective, Afghanistan is a party to the Geneva Conventions, including Geneva Convention IV,

²³ Laurie R. Blank 'Taking Distinction to the Next Level: Accountability for Fighters' Failure to Distinguish Themselves from Civilians' 2016 (46)3 *Valparaiso University Law Review* at 765.

²⁴ O Hegay 'Meanings and Causes of Terrorism and Its Implications and Threats for International Peace and Stability' (2006) Thesis Submitted to KDI School of Public Policy and Management for the degree of Master of Public Policy at 9 – 10.

²⁵ A Mir, 'Two Years Under the Taliban: Is Afghanistan a Terrorist Safe Haven Once Again?' United States Institute of Peace, 15th August 2023, available at <https://www.usip.org/publications/2023/08/two-years-under-taliban-afghanistan-terrorist-safe-haven-once-again>, accessed on 14 October 2024.

and is bound by their terms and provisions.²⁶ Furthermore, Afghanistan has ratified most of the major international agreements on the protection of human rights.²⁷ The Taliban government quickly regained control of Afghanistan and imposed a repressive regime resulting in the regression of human rights, including public executions, amputations, flogging, severe restraints on women's rights, torture, enforced disappearance, and so on.²⁸ The ISKP which has been the most active terrorist organization in Afghanistan since 2021 is responsible for the third most deaths globally, and gained international attention after killing 170 Afghan civilians and 13 United States soldiers in 2021.²⁹ In the same year, the ISKP staged 365 terrorist attacks in Afghanistan leading to 2,210 casualties.³⁰ In violation of the laws of war, the ISKP continues to target civilians in Afghanistan and beyond, by bombings and other attacks.³¹ On 22 March 2024, an ISKP attack killed 140

²⁶ J Jery 'Al Qaeda and Taliban Detainees – An Examination of Legal Rights and Appropriate Treatment' in Fred L. Borch and Paul. S. Wilson (Eds), *International Law and the War on Terror*, *International Law Studies*, 2003 (79) at 442 – 454.

²⁷ N Andihsa 'Opening Remarks of Amb. Nasir Andihsa at the Human Rights Council, 46th Session', Universal Periodic Review – Geneva, 29th April 2024', available at https://uprmeetings.ohchr.org/Sessions/46/Afghanistan/DL_UPRDocuments/Afghanistan_State%20under%20review_opening%20statement.docx#:~:text=The%20state%20of%20Afghanistan%2C%20as,and%20Cultural%20Rights%2C%20the%20Convention, accessed on 14 October 2024. For example, the Convention on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination 1965, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966, Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984, the Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women 1979, and the Convention of the Rights of the Child 1989.

²⁸ Centre for Preventive Action. 'Instability in Afghanistan' 1 July 2024, available at <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/war-afghanistan>, accessed on 14 October 2024.

²⁹ A Dawi, 'Afghanistan Tops 2021 Global Survey of Islamic State Casualties' 27 January 2022, available at <https://www.voanews.com/a/afghanistan-tops-2021-global-survey-of-islamic-state-casualties-/6415735.html>, accessed on 30 October 2024.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Centre for Preventive Action 'Instability in Afghanistan' 1 July 2024, available at <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/war-afghanistan>, accessed on 14 October 2024.

people in Moscow.³² Despite the importance of this discussion, modes of enforcement of IHL, the repression of grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions of 1949; accountability for war crimes or international crimes, and state responsibility for violations of obligations under IHL or human rights regimes are beyond the scope of this paper.

The Saint Petersburg Declaration of 1868 which espoused the rule that the legitimate object which states should strive to accomplish during armed conflict is to weaken the military forces of the adversary, was underpinned by the need to distinguish between civilians and combatants.³³ The Hague Regulations of 1907 contained a provision with a similar effect.³⁴

Therefore, no claim to military necessity could justify any direct attacks on civilians or civilian objects. It is through the operational observance of the principle of distinction that IHL can perform its role of insulating civilian populations from harm during armed conflicts. Although this grundnorm proposition appears as a simple theoretical construct, in practice, its implementation faces tremendous challenges. Modern warfare is characterized by an increasing blurring of the distinction between combatants and civilians and the intermingling of military structures and civilian establishments.

³² STIMSON 'Afghanistan's Evolving Terrorism Landscape under the Taliban' 14 August 2024, available at <https://www.stimson.org/event/afghanistans-evolving-terrorism-landscape-under-the-taliban/>, accessed on 14 October 2024.

³³ Declaration Renouncing the Use, in Time of War, of Explosive Projectiles under 400 Grammes Weight, November 29/December 11 1868.

³⁴ Article 25: The attack or bombardment, by whatever means, of towns, villages, dwellings, or buildings which are undefended is prohibited. Convention (IV) Respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land and its Annex: Regulations Concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land. The Hague, 18 October 1907.

IHL acknowledges the fact that not all civilians abstain from hostilities; civilians deserve more protection than others, and generally, civilians who participate in hostilities lose their protected status.³⁵ In reality today, the assumption that armed conflict is the privilege of the armed forces of states and that civilians are removed from engaging in the conflict and therefore, deserving of protection, is fast becoming illusory.

The distinction principle is applicable to international and non-international armed conflicts. The principle of distinction is contained in Articles 48, 51; 52 of Additional Protocol I of 1977, and 13 of Additional Protocol II. The principle has been affirmed by other treaties on means of warfare.³⁶ The principle of distinction stipulated in Article 48 of Additional Protocol I provides that “In order to ensure respect for and protection of the civilian population and civilian objects, the Parties to the conflict shall at all times distinguish between the civilian population and combatants and between civilian objects and military objectives and accordingly shall direct their operations only against military objectives.”³⁷ The principle of distinction has been pronounced upon by national and international courts. In the *Nuclear Weapons Advisory Opinion*, the International Court of Justice said: “The cardinal principles contained in the texts constituting the fabric of humanitarian law are the following. The first is aimed at the protection of

³⁵ M Avril. ‘The challenges to International Humanitarian Law and the principles of distinction and protection from the increased participation of civilians in hostilities’ *Spotlight on Issues of Contemporary Concern in International Humanitarian Law and International Criminal Law* (2004) at 2.

³⁶ See for example, Protocol on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Incendiary Weapons, Geneva, 10 October 1980, (Protocol III). Article 2 prohibits attacks by incendiary weapons on civilians and civilian objects.

³⁷ Article 48, Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflict (Protocol I), of 8 June 1977.

the civilian population and civilian objects and establishes the distinction between combatants and non-combatants; States must never make civilians the object of attack courts...”³⁸ This position was adopted by the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) in *Prosecutor v Stanislav Galic* when the tribunal noted that the prohibition against attacking civilians stems from a fundamental principle of international humanitarian law - the principle of distinction.³⁹ Similarly, in *Prosecutor v Dragomir Milosevic*, the Appeals Chamber of the ICTY in its judgment, held that in customary international law, there is an absolute prohibition against targeting the civilian population, encompassing indiscriminate attacks. Furthermore, the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) in its commentary emphasized that the principle has assumed the status of customary international law.⁴⁰ A breach of the principle of distinction, leading to attacks against civilians, constitutes a war crime.⁴¹

3. Military objectives and civilian objects

The only legitimate object that States should endeavor to accomplish during war is to weaken the military forces of the enemy.⁴² While combatants and military objectives may be legitimately targeted, civilians and civilian objects must be spared. The ICRC has described the principle as a norm of

³⁸ Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons, Advisory Opinion, 8 July 1996, ICJ Rep. 1996, para.78, p. 226.

³⁹ *The Prosecutor v Stanislav Galic (Trial and Opinion)* International Criminal Tribunal (ICTY) Trial Chamber I, IT-98-29-T, 5 December 2003.

⁴⁰ IHL Database; Customary IHL. Rule 1. The Principle of Distinction between Civilians and Combatants available at https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/customary-ihl/eng/docindex/v1_rul_rule1#refFn_D70F41D7_00003, accessed on 10 April 2022.

⁴¹ Article 8 (2) (b) (i) and Article 8 (2) (e) (i) of the Statute of the International Court of Justice, 1998.

⁴² Declaration Renouncing the Use, in Time of War, of Explosive Projectiles under 400 Grammes Weight, November 29th /December 11th 1868.

customary international law applicable to both international and non-international armed conflicts.⁴³ All objects which are not military objectives are civilian objects.⁴⁴ The rule that attacks should be directed against only military objects is a part of the principle of distinction in Article 48 of Additional Protocol I. The rule is essential for the protection of civilians in armed conflict. Article 52 (2) of AP I states that “Attacks shall be limited strictly to military objectives. In so far as objects are concerned, military objectives are limited to those objects which by their nature, location, purpose, or use make an effective contribution to military action and whose total or partial destruction, capture or neutralization, in the circumstances ruling at the time, offers a definite military advantage.”⁴⁵ In the laws of war, the word “attack” means acts of violence against the adversary, whether in offence or in defence.⁴⁶

The major condition in Article 52 (2) of Additional Protocol I is that the destruction of an object arises from its military use rather than to terrorize or weaken civilians. In consequence, the nature, place, purpose or use of the object must effectively contribute to military action; and secondly, the total or partial destruction, capture or neutralization must offer a specified

⁴³ IHL Database-Customary IHL, ‘Definition of Civilian Objects’, available at https://www.ihl-databases.icrc.org/customary-ihl/eng/docindex/v1_rul_rule9#:~:text=The%20definition%20of%20civilian%20objects,objects%20are%20protected%20against%20attack, accessed 27 April 2022

⁴⁴ Article 52 (1), Additional Protocol I of 1977.

⁴⁵ See also Article 2 of the 1907 Hague Convention (IX) under which the bombardment of military works, military or naval establishments, depots of arms or war *matériel*, workshops or plants which could be utilized for the needs of the hostile fleet or army, and the ships of war in the harbor, is lawful. By Article 24 (2) of The Hague Rules of Air Warfare 1923, ‘factories constituting important and well-known centres engaged in the manufacture of arms, ammunition or distinctively military supplies’ are military objectives.

⁴⁶ Article 49 (1), Additional Protocol I, 1977. Military Objectives, The Practical Guide to Humanitarian Law, available at <https://guide-humanitarian-law.org/content/article/3/military-objectives/>, accessed on 13 April 2022.

military advantage. If a question arises whether an object which is regularly used for civilian purposes, such as a place of worship, house or other dwelling or a school, is being used to make an effective contribution to military action, there shall be a presumption of its civilian use.⁴⁷

The ICRC's illustrative list of civilian objects is helpful, viz:

Civilian areas, towns, cities, villages, residential areas, dwellings, buildings and houses and schools, civilian means of transportation, hospitals, medical establishments and medical units, historic monuments, places of worship and cultural property, and the natural environment, as *prima facie* civilian objects, provided, in the final analysis, they have not become military objectives.⁴⁸

Military objectives do not lose their character as such because of the presence of civilians in them, rather, the civilians are taken to have assumed the risks incidental to being there. Chapter IV (Articles 57-58) of Additional Protocol I dealing with "precautionary measures" during attacks, places a responsibility upon military commanders to ensure the exercise of care or precaution to spare civilians from attacks.

The precautionary measures include (a) doing everything feasible to verify that the objectives to be attacked are neither civilians nor civilian objects and are not subject to special protection but are military objectives: (b) taking all feasible precautions in the choice of means and methods of attack in

⁴⁷ Article 52 (3) of AP I of 1977.

⁴⁸ IHL Database-Customary IHL, 'Definition of Civilian Objects', available < https://www.ihl-databases.icrc.org/customaryihl/eng/docindex/v1_rul_rule9#:~:text=The%20definition%20of%20civilian%20objects,objects%20are%20protected%20against%20attack >, accessed on 30 October 2024; See also *Prosecutor v Blaskic* (ICTY Trial Chamber) 3 March 2000 paras 401, 509–510.

order to avoid, or minimize incidental loss of civilian life, injury to civilians and damage to civilian objects; (c) refraining from launching an attack which may cause incidental loss of civilian life, injury to civilians, and, or damage to civilian objects, which would be excessive in relation to the concrete and direct military advantage anticipated; and (d) giving an effective advance warning of attacks which may affect the civilian population, unless circumstances do not permit. Belligerents faced with making a choice between several military objectives which may yield a similar military advantage are required to select the objective which will cause the least danger to civilians and civilian objects, upon attack.⁴⁹

4. Who is a combatant?

Khen expresses the view that the legal justification for the development of the principle of distinction in IHL is derived from the just war tradition which was strongly influenced by the writings of Thomas Aquinas.⁵⁰ The doctrine created rules governing the morality of pursuing war (*jus ad bellum*), and permissible conduct in war (*jus in bello*). The traditional just war doctrine created two categories of victims of armed conflict: combatants and noncombatants. Although placing no limitations on the killing of combatants, the theory excused the killing of non-combatants only unintentionally and, even then, only if the harm they suffer is necessary and proportionate to the intended goals of the attack.⁵¹

⁴⁹ Article 57 (3) of Additional Protocol I, 1977.

⁵⁰ Hilly Moodrick-Even Khen, 'Reaffirming the Distinction between Combatants and Civilians: The Cases of the Israeli Army's "Hannibal Directive" and the United States' Drone Airstrikes against ISIS' 2016 (33)3 *Arizona Journal of International and Comparative Law* at 766

⁵¹ War, Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, (May 3 2016), available at < <https://www.plato.stanford.edu/entries/war/index.html#ref-17> >, accessed on 26 April 2022.

Only combatants are entitled to use force in armed conflict. Combatants are legitimate military objectives. Combatants are obliged to comply with the rules of IHL.⁵² Except where they have breached the provisions of the Geneva Conventions, combatants cannot be prosecuted merely for taking part in hostilities as they enjoy combatant immunity or belligerent privilege. The term 'combatant' is used only in reference to an IAC. Generally speaking, combatant refers to members of the armed forces (except medical personnel and chaplains); members of militias, volunteer corps and resistance movements belonging to a party to the conflict, and civilians in a *levee en mass*.

The ICRC is of the view that the classic definition of combatants, including 'all members of the armed forces of a party to the conflict except medical and religious personnel' is a norm of the customary international law of armed conflict.⁵³ As Kenneth Watkin stated 'acting on behalf of a state has constituted the primary means of attaining combatant, and therefore legitimate, status.'⁵⁴

The interrelation of Article 4 of the Third Geneva Convention and Article 43 of Additional Protocol I yields the context of the term, combatant. Article 4 of the Third Geneva Convention of 1949 provides for the class of individuals, including armed forces, entitled to the prisoner of war (POW) status upon capture. On the other hand, Article 43 of Additional Protocol I state the armed forces' composition.

⁵² Articles 43 (1) and 44 (2) of Additional Protocol I, 1977.

⁵³ IHL Database, 'Rule 3. Definition of Combatants', available at < https://www.ihl-databases.icrc.org/customary-ihl/eng/docs/v1_rul_rule3 >, accessed on 20 April 2022.

⁵⁴ Kenneth Watkin, *Warriors Without Rights? Combatants, Unprivileged Belligerents, and the Struggle for Legitimacy* 2005(2) *Program on Humanitarian Policy and Conflict Research Harvard University Occasional Paper Series Winter* at 5.

It is generally understood that armed forces may consist of combatants and non-combatants.⁵⁵ Medical and religious personnel in the armed forces are not regarded as combatants, although upon capture by the enemy, they fall under a special regime of protection. They may be retained by the adverse party only as far as the health and religious needs of POWs dictate.⁵⁶ In other words, their retention is for the purpose of assisting POWs. During their retention, the captured medical personnel and chaplains are entitled to respect and protection under the conventions in all circumstances.⁵⁷ Personnel whose retention is not indispensable will be returned to their party as soon as roads are open or military requirements allow.⁵⁸

Only combatants in the armed forces constitute legitimate objects of attack. Non-combatants retain protection from attacks as long as they abstain from direct participation in hostilities. Non-combatants in the armed forces are entitled to varying levels of protection depending upon their statuses. In the *Tadic* case, the ICTY Appeals Chamber held that Article 4 (A) (1) and (2) of GC III, established the requirements for the status of lawful combatants.⁵⁹ In Article 43 of AP I, the armed forces of a Party to a conflict consists of (1) all organized armed forces, groups and units which are under a command responsible to that Party for the conduct of its subordinates,

⁵⁵ Article 3 of The Hague Regulations of 1899: "The armed forces of the belligerent parties may consist of combatants and non-combatants". See also Article 3 of The Hague Regulations of 1907.

⁵⁶ Article 28 GC I.

⁵⁷ Article 31 GC I, & Article 33 GC III.

⁵⁸ Article 30 GC I.

⁵⁹ *Prosecutor v Dusko Tadic* Case No. IT-94-1-A, 15 July 1999, available at <https://www.icty.org/x/file/Legal%20Library/jud_supplement/supp6-e/tadic.htm>, accessed on 27 April 2022.

even if that Party is represented by a government or an authority not recognized by an adverse Party...;

(2) Members of the armed forces of a Party to a conflict (other than medical personnel and chaplains covered by Article 33 of the Third Convention) are combatants, that is to say, they have the right to participate directly in hostilities, and (3) Whenever a Party to a conflict incorporates a paramilitary or armed law enforcement agency into its armed forces it shall so notify the other Parties to the conflict.

Article 4 (A) (2) of GC IV stipulates a number of conditions that must be fulfilled by militias, volunteer corps, and resistance movements belonging to a party before they can enjoy the combatant status: (a) being commanded by a person responsible for his subordinates; (b) having a fixed distinctive sign recognizable at a distance; (c) carrying arms openly; and (d) conducting their operations in accordance with the laws and customs of war. Individuals who do not meet the conditions in Article 4 of the GC IV will nevertheless enjoy the fundamental guarantees in Article 75 of Additional Protocol I.

Combatants are entitled to POW status upon their capture by enemy forces. A wide array of protections is available for POWs, under the Third Geneva Convention including; humane treatment; freedom from physical mutilation, medical experiments;⁶⁰ respect for their person and honour;⁶¹ free maintenance and medical attention;⁶² equality of treatment;⁶³ retention of personal property, correspondence with family, and reception of aid from the ICRC.

⁶⁰ Article 13 GC III.

⁶¹ Article 14 GC III.

⁶² Article 15 GC III.

⁶³ Article 16 GC III.

5. Non-state actors in a non-international armed conflict

To avoid granting any iota of legitimacy to insurgents, Additional Protocol II does not confer combatant status on opposing non-state actors in an internal armed conflict. The consequence is that armed fighters on the opposing side are technically regarded as civilians who have illegally taken up arms against the state. Moreover, rebel forces or fighters may lack the identification criteria in Article 4 (2) of the Third Geneva Convention, thereby making it difficult to identify and separate them for attack.⁶⁴ Article 3 of the GC Conventions and Article I of Additional Protocol II mention 'armed forces, dissident armed forces, organized groups under a responsible command', but do not talk about combatants. The legal regime for internal armed conflicts does not provide for a distinction between combatants and civilians, combatant immunity, combatant privilege or POW treatment for non-state actors; rebels, terrorists, guerillas or irregulars, upon capture. It is, therefore, necessary to understand the circumstances under which civilians may lose their protection in a NIAC.

As most modern armed conflicts are asymmetrical, a large number of persons fighting against the state have no combatant privilege under the laws of war and may be treated as mere criminals by the state and even punished for merely taking up arms. However, at the end of hostilities, states are encouraged to grant amnesty to those who participated in the conflict.⁶⁵ It

⁶⁴ E Newalsing (2008), "Jean-Marie Henckaerts and Louise Doswald-Beck (eds.), *Customary International Humanitarian Law*, Geneva and Cambridge, International Committee of the Red Cross and Cambridge University Press 2005 (2)4 at 411.

⁶⁵ Article 6 (5), Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts (Protocol II) of 8 June 1977.

has been pointed out that the provisions of Additional Protocol II which apply to NIACs are considerably underdeveloped when compared to Additional Protocol I which applies to IACs, and as such, questions on combatant status and combatant immunity during NIACs have still not been satisfactorily answered.⁶⁶ Many problems arise in a NIAC when an attempt is made to apply the principle of distinction to internal armed conflicts. The rebels or insurgents may deliberately choose not to wear a distinguishing uniform in order to properly mix up with the rest of the civilian population.⁶⁷ Moreover, rebels or terrorists like the Boko Haram deliberately disregard the distinction principle or other rules of warfare to attack civilians to gain publicity or spread terror.⁶⁸

By special concession, a state may agree to grant non-state actors or irregular fighters combatant privilege. Otherwise, irregulars are regarded as civilians who have unlawfully, directly participated in hostilities and can be prosecuted under the domestic criminal laws of the state. They are usually regarded as outlaws or terrorists and may also be tried for grave breaches of IHL.⁶⁹ Irregular fighters do not constitute a specific legally defined group under IHL.⁷⁰ In some instances, irregulars have been described as ‘unlawful combatants’ in order to exclude

⁶⁶ D Bethlehem, and Others, ‘Classification of Conflicts: The Way Forward’ *International Law Meeting Summary*. (Chatham House October 1 2012), available at < <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/public/Research/International%20Law/011012summary.pdf> >, accessed on 26 April 2022.

⁶⁷ M Sassoli, “Terrorism and war” 2006(3) *Journal of International Criminal Justice* at 3.

⁶⁸ Human Rights Watch. Cameroon: Boko Haram Attacks Escalate in Far North, available at <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/04/05/cameroon-boko-haram-attacks-escalate-far-north> accessed on 3 April 2024.

⁶⁹ P Rowe, Freedom Fighters and Rebels: The Rules of Civil War 2002 (95)1 *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* at 3-4.

⁷⁰ Mediciens Sans Frontieres, ‘Combatants’ The Practical Guide to Humanitarian Law, available at < <https://www.guide-humanitarian-law.org/content/article/3/combatants/> >, accessed on 22 April 2022.

them from the IHL regime of protection. For participating directly in the armed conflict, they were not regarded as civilians, but they also failed to satisfy the conditions for POW or combatants. However, the courts have rejected the notion of the existence of a third category of individuals beyond combatants and civilians and held that they are civilians taking part in hostilities.⁷¹

6. Civilians

Despite the fact that the protection of civilians occupies a hallowed place in IHL, civilian populations often found themselves in dire conditions in armed conflicts around the globe in 2023.⁷² A United Nations report on trends on the impact of armed conflict on children and violations committed reported the recruitment and use of children, the killing and maiming of children, rape and other forms of sexual violence perpetrated against children, attacks on schools, and the abduction of children in conflicts in Israel, the Occupied Palestine, Burkina Faso, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Myanmar, Somalia, the Sudan, the Syrian Arab Republic, Ukraine and so on.⁷³ It is worth pointing out that unlike ancient warfare which was often characterized by the absence of a systematic protection for civilian populations, contemporary international law has established a complex network of regimes to protect

⁷¹ See *Public Committee against Torture in Israel v the Government of Israel et al.*, HCl 769/02, Judgment, 11 December 2005). See also *Hamdan v Rumsfeld*, 548 U.S. [2006].

⁷² “We Must Go Above, Beyond Compliance, Fully Protect Civilians Against ‘Harms They Are Suffering on Our Watch’ Senior Humanitarian Official Tells Security Council”. United Nations, SC/15702 21 May 2024, available at <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15702.doc.htm>, accessed on 13 October 2024.

⁷³ “Promotion and Protection of the Rights of Children”, United Nations, General Assembly, Security Council, Seventy-Eight Session, A/78/842-S/2024/384. 3rd June 2024, available at <https://www.un.org/sexualviolenceinconflict/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Children-and-armed-conflict.pdf>, accessed on 30 October 2024.

the rights of civilians in times of peace and armed conflict. It is also worth mentioning that human rights norms have a noticeable symbiotic effect on IHL through the process of interpreting IHL norms in conformity with human rights principles, and the mutual, concurrent application of human rights alongside IHL in armed conflicts.⁷⁴

According to Chris Wigwe, the regime for the protection of civilians basically consists of the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their protocols; the Law of The Hague, customary international humanitarian law, and other treaties on human rights.⁷⁵ For NIACs, the provisions on the protection of civilians are contained in Article 3 Common to the Four Geneva Conventions as well as Additional Protocol II. In *Prosecutor v Semanza*, the ICTR Trial Chamber held that both Common Article 3 and Additional Protocol II protect persons not taking an active part in the hostilities.⁷⁶ Maintaining a similar tone, the trial chamber of the ICTR in *Prosecutor v. Ntakirutimana and Ntakirutimana* noted that Article 4 of Additional Protocol II seeks to protect persons not taking an active part in the hostilities in armed conflicts, not of an international character.”

By mandating humane treatment in all circumstances, without any adverse distinction founded on race, colour, religion or faith, sex, birth or wealth, or any other similar criteria, for civilians who are not taking an active part in hostilities, Common Article 3 provides a sweeping regime of protection for civilian populations. The specific protections in Common Article 3 include the prohibition against violence to life, taking of

⁷⁴ RV Steenberghe ‘The Impacts of Human Rights Law on the Regulation of Armed Conflict: A Coherency-Based Approach to Dealing with both the ‘Interpretation’ and ‘Application’ Processes’ 2022 (104)919 *International Review of the Red Cross* at 1345 – 1396.

⁷⁵ CC Wigwe ‘International Humanitarian Law’ (2010) Readwide Publishers at 127.

⁷⁶ *The Prosecutor v Semanza* (ICTR Trial Chamber) (2003) paras 363-366.

hostages, outrages against personal dignity, and extra-judicial sentencing and executions.⁷⁷ There appear to be no major distinctions between IACs and NIACs in matters concerning the conduct of military operations.⁷⁸ The ICRC has poignantly posited that from a humanitarian perspective, there should be no distinction between the victims of IACs and NIACs in the application of IHL rules because they face similar problems and need comparable protections. Moreover, in both situations, fighters and civilians are arrested and detained by “the enemy”; civilians face forcible displacement; and cities where they live fall under enemy control. Attacks are launched against towns and villages, food supplies need to transit through the front lines, and the same weapons are used.⁷⁹ The Fourth Geneva Convention covers the protection of civilians during hostilities.⁸⁰ The defining feature of the convention is the insulation of civilian populations from the horrors of war, including murder, torture, and discrimination. Furthermore, the convention provides special regimes of protection for the wounded, children and pregnant women. The Fourth Geneva Convention provides direction, minimum standards, and rules for occupying powers.⁸¹ The regime of protection extends to the entire civilian populations of parties to an armed conflict.⁸² Civilians are protected from murder, torture, corporal punishment and medical experiments which are not necessitated by the medical treatment of a protected person.⁸³

⁷⁷ Common Article 3 (1) (a-d).

⁷⁸ CC Wigwe (2010) (n 76 above) at 128.

⁷⁹ Non-International Armed Conflict. ICRC, available at <https://casebook.icrc.org/law/non-international-armed-conflict>, accessed on 13 October 2024.

⁸⁰ Geneva Convention Relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, 12 August 1949.

⁸¹ The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and Additional Protocols, available at <https://www.colombohurdlaw.com/geneva-conventions-of-1949-additional-protocols/>, accessed on 13 October 2024.

⁸² Article 13 GC IV, 1949.

⁸³ Article 32 GC IV, 1949.

Civilian hospitals and their personnel are protected from attack.⁸⁴ Parties to an armed conflict are obliged to accord respect for the safety, honour, family rights, religious practices of civilians, and protect them from violence, insults and public curiosity.⁸⁵ Collective punishment, pillage, reprisals, indiscriminate destruction of property, and the taking of hostages are prohibited by IHL.⁸⁶ There are special obligations of occupying powers to civilian populations. For example, occupying powers are required to allow the passage of medical supplies and objects used for religious worship into occupied territory.⁸⁷ This duty includes the provision of food and medical supplies to the occupied territory, as well as the maintenance of medical and public health facilities. Additional Protocol I provides a broad spectrum of protection to the civilian population. Thus, the civilian population and individual civilians shall enjoy general protection against dangers arising from military operations.⁸⁸ This protection covers journalists,⁸⁹

⁸⁴ Article 18 GC IV, 1949.

⁸⁵ Article 27 GC IV, 1949.

⁸⁶ Articles 33 – 34 GC IV, 1949.

⁸⁷ Article 55 and 58, GC IV, 1949.

⁸⁸ Article 51, Additional Protocol I. — Protection of the civilian population:

1. The civilian population and individual civilians shall enjoy general protection against dangers arising from military operations. To give effect to this protection, the following rules, which are additional to other applicable rules of international law, shall be observed in all circumstances.

2. The civilian population as such, as well as individual civilians, shall not be the object of attack. Acts or threats of violence the primary purpose of which is to spread terror among the civilian population are prohibited.

3. Civilians shall enjoy the protection afforded by this Section, unless and for such time as they take a direct part in hostilities.

4. Indiscriminate attacks are prohibited. Indiscriminate attacks are: *a*) those which are not directed at a specific military objective; *b*) those which employ a method or means of combat which cannot be directed at a specific military objective; or *c*) those which employ a method or means of combat the effects of which cannot be limited as required by this Protocol; and consequently, in each such case, are of a nature to strike military objectives and civilians or civilian objects without distinction.

5. Among others, the following types of attacks are to be considered as indiscriminate: *a*) an attack by bombardment by any methods or means which treats as a single military objective a number of clearly separated and distinct military objectives located in a city,

civilian medical personnel,⁹⁰ women and children.⁹¹ It is prohibited to subject children to indecent assault. Parties to armed conflict are required to implement measures to prevent children who have not attained the age of 15 from taking a direct part in hostilities or from being recruited into the army. In addition, Article 76 of Additional Protocol I state that women shall be the object of special respect and shall be protected in particular against rape, forced prostitution and any other form of indecent assault.

In some conflicts, the deliberate targeting and subjection of civilians to gross atrocities have been reported. By 31st August, the UN Human Rights Monitoring Mission in Ukraine (HRMMU) had verified that war-related violence in the Russo-Ukraine armed conflict had led to the deaths of 11,743 civilians and injured 24,614 in Ukraine since 24th February 2022. The findings were that the Russian armed army had continued to target energy infrastructure across Ukraine, disrupting essential services and worsening the plight of the civilian population.⁹²

town, village or other area containing a similar concentration of civilians or civilian objects; and b) an attack which may be expected to cause incidental loss of civilian life, injury to civilians, damage to civilian objects, or a combination thereof, which would be excessive in relation to the concrete and direct military advantage anticipated.

6. Attacks against the civilian population or civilians by way of reprisals are prohibited.

7. The presence or movements of the civilian population or individual civilians shall not be used to render certain points or areas immune from military operations, in particular in attempts to shield military objectives from attacks or to shield, favour or impede military operations. The Parties to the conflict shall not direct the movement of the civilian population or individual civilians in order to attempt to shield military objectives from attacks or to shield military operations.

⁸⁹ Article 79 AP I, 1977.

⁹⁰ Article 15 AP I, 1977.

⁹¹ Article 77 AP I, 1977.

⁹² 40th Periodic Report on Human Rights Situations in Ukraine: Treatment of Prisoners of War and Update on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine 1 June 2024 – 31 August 2024 (1 October 2024), available at <https://www.ohchr.org/en/documents/country-reports/40th-periodic-report-human-rights-situation-ukraine-treatment-prisoners>, accessed on 14 October 2024.

Attacks on civilians ignore the foundational principles of IHL, which include distinguishing between civilians and combatants, and respect for human life. Violations of IHL show that parties to armed conflicts are failing to take up their responsibilities of protecting civilians. The enforcement of IHL is centred on the role of states. States have to enact measures to ensure respect for IHL before, during and at the cessation of hostilities.

As long as civilians do not take a direct part in hostilities, they are not to be considered objects of attack.⁹³ However, with the increasing use of civilians by the armed forces to perform tasks previously reserved for military personnel, there appears to be a seamless transition from civilian to combatant, and the attendant direct or indirect participation in hostilities. This scenario may arise even when the individual does not openly bear arms or wear distinguishing uniforms. One of the unfinished tasks of IHL is to propose criteria for determining when an individual has crossed the line between civilian status and combatant. A civilian is defined negatively as any individual who is not a combatant or a member of the armed forces.⁹⁴ In *Prosecutor v Kayishema and Ruzindana*, the Trial Chamber of the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) said “all persons who are not combatants might be considered civilians.”⁹⁵

The civilian population consists of all persons who are not combatants.⁹⁶ In the event of doubt on whether an individual is a civilian or not, he is regarded as one.⁹⁷ The decision of the

⁹³ Article 51 (3) of Additional Protocol I, 1977.

⁹⁴ Article 50 (1) of Additional Protocol I, 1977.

⁹⁵ *The Prosecutor v Kayishema and Ruzindana* (Trial Chamber), May 21, 1999, para 179-180.

⁹⁶ Article 50 (2) of Additional Protocol II, 1977.

⁹⁷ Article 50 (1) of Additional Protocol I, 1977.

International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) in *Prosecutor v Akayesu* was that:

Members of the civilian population are people who are not taking any active part in the hostilities, including members of the armed forces who laid down their arms and those persons placed *hors de combat* by sickness, wounds, detention or any other cause.⁹⁸

Unlike combatants, civilians do not have the right to participate in hostilities and may be prosecuted for violating the penal laws of their states or for war crimes. On the other hand, civilian nationals of a party to the conflict who have not participated in hostilities but have found themselves in the power of the enemy are entitled to the protections in Article 75 of Additional Protocol I.

Article 75 of AP I protect such individuals from violence to life, health, or physical or mental well-being: murder, torture of all kinds, whether physical or mental, corporal punishment, mutilation, outrages upon personal dignity, in particular humiliating and degrading treatment, enforced prostitution and any form of indecent assault, the taking of hostages, and collective punishments.

Civilians who participate in hostilities and have fallen into the hands of the adverse party shall be presumed to be POWs, and be protected by the Third Geneva Convention.⁹⁹ Any doubt arising on the entitlement of such an individual to the POW status would be resolved by a competent tribunal, but until that time, he would continue to enjoy the status of a POW.

⁹⁸ *Prosecutor v Akayesu* ICTR (Trial Chamber) 2 September 1998, para 582.

⁹⁹ Article 45 (I) of Additional Protocol I of 1977.

7. The notion of direct participation in hostilities

Despite being used as the central criterion for determining whether civilians have lost their legal right to protection under IHL, the notion of ‘direct participation in hostilities’ has not been defined in the Geneva Conventions. Hostilities have two elements; the temporal element, and the material element. While the former refers to the time spent on preparation, executing and withdrawing from an attack, the material element covers the actual attack itself. The ICRC in its Commentary on the Additional Protocols expressed the view that the word “hostilities” covers not only the time that the civilian actually makes use of a weapon but also, for example, the time that he is carrying it, as well as situations in which he undertakes hostile acts without using a weapon.’¹⁰⁰ All acts of hostilities until the resolution of the conflict comprise an ‘armed conflict’. For a civilian to directly participate in hostilities, he must have engaged in a specific attack or attacks upon the opposing forces or objects during an armed conflict. According to the ICRC, there are two basic conditions in the notion of direct participation in hostilities. Firstly, there must be ‘hostilities’ and secondly, there must be ‘direct participation.’¹⁰¹ While the concept of hostilities refers to the collective resort to the means and methods of injuring the enemy, participation in hostilities covers an individual’s involvement in hostilities. To be regarded as direct participants in the conflict, civilians do not have to be in the theatre of confrontations or where hostilities are conducted. Civilians can directly participate in

¹⁰⁰ *Commentary on the Additional Protocols of 8 June 1977 to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949*, Y. Sandoz, C. Swinarki and B. Zimmerman, eds. (Geneva, ICRC/Martinus Nijhoff 1987) (Geneva, ICRC 1987) at 618-619.

¹⁰¹ Nils Melzer ICRC Interpretive Guidance on the Notion of Direct Participation in Hostilities under International Humanitarian Law at 43 May 2009. ICRC, Geneva, Switzerland.

hostilities by rendering tactical support to military operations. For example, providing aerial surveillance or gathering intelligence by complex computer networks, or manning advanced weapons systems will be regarded as direct participation in hostilities, which will result in the loss of protection from attacks. International Criminal Tribunals have elaborated on the concept of direct participation in hostilities. While restating the rule that civilians will lose their right to protection as civilians *per se* if they participate in hostilities, the trial chamber of the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) in *Prosecutor v Rutaganda*, held that “to take a ‘direct’ part in the hostilities means acts of war which by their nature or purpose are likely to cause actual harm to the personnel and equipment of the enemy armed forces.”¹⁰² The ICTR explained further that because the class of civilians is broadly defined “it will be a matter of evidence on a case-by-case basis to determine whether a victim has the status of civilian.” In another case, *the Prosecutor v Semanza*, the ICTR Trial Chamber declared that “the question to be answered is whether, at the time of the alleged offence, the alleged victim was directly taking part in the hostilities. If the answer is negative, the alleged victim was a person protected by Common Article 3 and Additional Protocol II. To take a direct part in hostilities means, for the purposes of these provisions, to engage in acts of war that strike at personnel or equipment of the enemy armed forces.”¹⁰³

¹⁰² *The Prosecutor v Rutaganda* (ICTR Trial Chamber) (1999) paras 100 -101.

¹⁰³ *Prosecutor v Semanza* (ICTR Trial Chamber) (2003) paras 363-366.

8. Challenges to the application of the principle of distinction

IHL evolved in an age characterized by the prevalence of inter-state armed conflicts, unlike today, where most conflicts are fought between states and non-state actors, or in contexts outside the contemplation of traditional norms of IHL. For reasons previously stated, the principle of distinction is not usually accorded respect in conflicts, where the opposing force is made up of civilians, insurgents and terrorists who have taken up arms against the state. The requirement of a distinction between combatants and military objectives on one hand, and civilians and civilian objects on the other hand, places enormous operational difficulties upon field commanders before launching attacks. The commander or combatant requires sufficient information to make that distinction in a very uncooperative war theatre. The commander may lack sufficient training in the laws of war or may have to make an instantaneous decision to attack without the opportunity to distinguish between targets, or even be incapable of making any distinction at all.¹⁰⁴

Dissidents may capture entire towns of civilians and prevent the inhabitants from leaving for the purpose of using them as human shields, as is being done by Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria.¹⁰⁵ This makes it difficult for the armed forces to direct attacks specifically at the terrorists as civilians have not been relocated to safe places. Another challenge posed by internal

¹⁰⁴ JP Kot, *Israeli Civilians versus Palestinian Combatants? Reading the Goldstone Report in Light of the Israeli Conception of the Principle of Distinction* 2011 (24)4 *Leiden Journal of International Law* at 961-988.

¹⁰⁵ G Birukila (2016) 11th April "A Harrowing Escape from Boko Haram", available at <https://www.unicef.org/stories/harrowing-escape-boko-haram-nigeria>, accessed on 2 April 2024.

armed conflicts is the epidemic of impunity on the part of the state's armed forces. Due to the application of the principle of state sovereignty, the internal affairs of the state, including the failure to distinguish between civilians and insurgents, and violations of IHL by counter-insurgents go unpunished and are shielded from external scrutiny. In recent years, an increasing number of military duties have been performed by civilian staff.

As military missions become more complex, civilians play a critical role in military engineering, and weapons systems, science, technology, mathematics, and cyber security, amongst numerous others. Some of the tasks performed by civilians may be regarded as direct participation in hostilities.¹⁰⁶ Some states, for example, the UK and USA have gone ahead to establish an Army Civil Service or Corps to provide critical or tactical support to the military combatants. Army civilians “serve in all theaters and are deployed throughout the world in support of the Army's missions, to include the Global War on Terrorism. Not only do they assist with many of the reconstruction projects in Iraq and Afghanistan, but Army civilians are also being recruited to fill other positions to support the war...they help train Soldiers for deployment and maintain the facilities while the Soldiers are away, defending our country...”¹⁰⁷ The reasons advanced for the growing reliance on civilians include the minimization of costs, as civilians cost less to maintain than military personnel. Moreover, the army's reliance on complex technology for warfare makes it necessary to use civilians to operate, manage

¹⁰⁶ ME Guillory, 'Civilianizing the Force: Is the United States Crossing the Rubicon?' 2001 (51) *Air Force Law Review* at 11.

¹⁰⁷ K Gan. Army Civilian Corps (January – March 2007), available at <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA592806>, accessed on 2 April 2024.

and maintain high-tech weapons systems.¹⁰⁸ Army civilians may be unaware that they have become legitimate targets because their activities amount to direct participation in hostilities. Coupled with this is the outsourcing of military functions to private companies, which are required to provide logistic and maintenance support. Defence contractors employ a large number of military veterans, now regarded as civilians, under the rules of IHL. On account of their significant military experience, they undertake tasks along the lines of direct participation in hostilities.

9. Conclusion

In this article, the position of combatants and civilians has been discussed. Presently, IHL recognizes only these two classes of individuals. The distinction between these combatants and civilians has historically been at the core of international humanitarian law. While combatants may be targeted, civilians are protected from attacks for as long as they refrain from participating in hostilities. Along with combatants, military objectives are also legitimate objects of attack, while civilian objects are immune from attack. This statement encapsulates the principle of distinction and the relevance of the distinction between combatants and civilians. Civilians who illegally participate in hostilities and find themselves in the power of the adverse party are not entirely outside the protection of the law. They are still entitled to the guarantees in Article 75 of Additional Protocol I.

¹⁰⁸ SM Gates and AA Robbert, *Comparing the Costs of DoD Military and Civil Service Personnel*, RAND National Defense Research Institute, MR-980-OSD, 1998.